

“Mit schwarz Grunde und Tapfer Keit”: The Military Record of Sgt. Paul Ernst Kaess
by Brian Paul Kaess¹

My Grandfather **Sgt. Paul Ernst Kaess** (1921-2002) served in the German Army in WWII, seeing extensive action during the conflict. Paul Ernst Kaess’ military record from the German Army in WWII was obtained from Deutsche Dienststelle Berlin (now Bundesarchiv-PA) in February 2017 by Brian Paul Kaess, his Grandson.

Paul’s entry date for the **German Army (Heer)** was June 17, 1940. He was captured on V-E Day (May 8, 1945) and released from being a POW on June 14, 1945, and may have been discharged that very same day. He attended Field Artillery training in **Batterie schwere Artillerie-Ersatz-Abteilung 61** in Pilsen (June 1940) and Schwabish Gmund (Sept 1940). He also trained with **Batterie Artillerie-Lehr- Regiment Juteborg** in Sept 1940. He was assigned to **Batterie Sturm-Artillerie- Abteilung 190** from October 1, 1940 to February 4, 1944. This was his **main unit**. A **Sturm Gesch. Lehr Brigade 190** is mentioned in his 1946 Denazification File as one of his units (from October 1, 1940 to January 3, 1944), so this sort of adds up with the above. The Sturm Artillerie units wore the uniforms of the Panzer Troops, and though initially assigned as infantry ground support, they evolved into a ‘tank destroyer’ role. From the Deutsche Dienststelle file, he also served in **Sturmgeschutz-Brigade 190** from January 14, 1944. Also mentioned in the 1946 Denazification File is **Schwers. Ers. Art. Abt. 61**, (from August 14, 1940 to December 1, 1940), similar to what is mentioned above in a training role in the Deutsche Dienststelle file. Originating from the latter, from February 24, 1944 to his discharge or an unknown date, he served in **Genesendenbatterie Sturmgeschutz-Ersatz- und Ausbildungs-Abteilung 200** in Schweinfurt. There is some slight overlap with regard to dates, but that is to be expected when Paul filled out the Denazification File info in Ludwigburg, Germany in 1946, some time after the events in question. It was amazing how precise he actually was! It can also be concluded that because the details provided in the transcribed/translated Deutsche Dienststelle file were similar or identical to what appears in the Denazification File, we therefore have a faithful rendering of valuable information regarding Paul’s service.

Paul was **in hospital** three times:

- 1) June 22, 1942 in Kreislazarett 2/610 **Simferopol** (Crimea)
- 2) January 30, 1944 to February 9 1944 in Reservelazarett I **Warschau** (Warsaw), C1, Salzstrasse
- 3) February 2, 1944 in Reservelazarett III **Hannover**, Abteilung Clementinenhaus Von Reservelazarett I **Warshau**.

Paul Ernst Kaess was promoted to **Gefreiter** (Corporal) in June 22, 1942 and promoted to **Unteroffizier** (Seargent) on Jan 30, 1944. He was captured by the Allies on May 8, 1945, or V-E Day.

¹ The phrase "mit Schwarz Grunde und Tapfer Keit" appears on the Wound Badge 3rd Class (Black) from WWII. The phrase reflects both the color of the badge and the valor of the recipient in the face of hostile action. It’s not an official motto but a poetic or commemorative inscription emphasizing courage in the face of injury. It was usually awarded to those wounded once or twice.

While looking for Carpentry Guild records for my Paternal Grandfather Paul Ernst Kaess (1921-2002), I managed to find his Denazification file in the **Staatsarchiv Ludwigsburg**, a branch of the Landesarchiv Baden-Württemberg in SW Germany. I inquired with **Hartmut Obst** and he said It was filed under signature **EL 902/15 Bü 10835**. He said they had a total of 24 pages for the file.

On March 7 2019, **Brian Paul Kaess** received a reply in Mexico from the Ludwigsburg archiv in his inbox with a zip file full of 17 pages of documents related to his Grandfather **Paul Ernst Kaess**. Jackpot! I found ten that I thought were valuable and loaded them onto familysearch community to be translated. I gave the documents various names: Annual Pay Rate, Arbeitsblatt, Associations, NSDAP/HJ statement, Party History, Foreign Travel, Unit location History, Personal Info, Paul Kaess statement & Spruckkammer.

Probably, the most valuable document at first glance to myself personally was 'Foreign Travel.' This confirmed that he had traveled (during wartime) to **France** (Frankreich), **Rumania** (Rumanien), **Bulgaria/Greece**, and **Russia** (Russland). For **Rumania**, he served there from January 20, 1941 to March 1, 1941. For Bulgaria and Greece, he served from March 5? 1941 until June 14, 1941. For France and Rumania, he was just training. He served in France from December 1, 1940 to January 1, 1941. This evidence about service in **France** helps lend credence to the family yarn that he had a French girlfriend. For **Russia**, he stated he had been there from June 22, 1941 until July 3 1944. June 22 1941 was the start of the Barbarossa campaign. We know from other sources that Paul was in the German Army from 1940 until 1944 (at least). Also, Paul stated in 1990 that he had been wounded in **Vilnius, Lithuania**, in 1944 when a Russian soldier had thrown a grenade into his armored vehicle. July 3, 1944 is right before the opening of the Russian **Vilnius Offensive**, during **Operation Bagration**, the Soviet's Great Summer Offensive of 1944. This July 3, 1944 date could easily have been the date Paul was wounded and evacuated from Russia. This would not have been the first time Paul was wounded. Medical Records also place him in **Warsaw, Poland** in early 1944. He was also in hospital in Crimea in 1942.

There was also a list of Medals/Awards at the bottom of the Military Service section. They read as follows:

- 1) **Ostmedalie** (Eastern Front Medal) 1942
- 2) **EK.II.** (Iron Cross 2nd Class) 1943
- 3) **EK.I.** (Iron Cross 1st Class) 1943
- 4) **Sturm abzekhev I.u.II.Stufe** (General Assault Badge 1st & 2nd steps) 1943
- 5) **Erwundstewabzeichen mit Schwarz Grunde und Tapfer Keit¹** 1944 or Wounds Badge 3rd Class (Black); also known in German as the **Verwundetenabzeichen in Schwarz**.

There was also an 'Arbeitsblatt' form, dated 27 Aug 1946. This form showed he had been in the HJ or **Hitler Youth** from 1934-1939. It also demonstrated that he had been a member of the **NSDAP** or **Nazi Party** from 1940 until 1945. One of the most revealing documents was his personal info, confirming much of what I had gathered over the years from other sources. His name is mentioned as Paul Kaess, born Feb 6 1921 in Benningen.

His occupation is 'Sitzmobiltischler' or seating furniture maker. His religion was Evangelisch or Lutheran. His citizenship is mentioned as 'Deutsch' or German. His address is Wilhelmstr. 17 in Heutingsheim, Germany. His hair color is Brown with his eyes Grey-Green. Even his weight is mentioned- 120 pf., whatever that is supposed to mean.

The unit location history is a chronological record of employment and military service/before/during the war, he had been first an Apprentice (from 1934-1939) and then a Journeyman Carpenter (from 1939-40). He had been a member of the **RAD or Reich Labour Force** from March 17, 1940 until June 10, 1940. He entered the German Army on June 17, 1940. His Ober Leutnant from 1940 to 1944 was named Naether or something similar. This could easily have been his friend 'Chef' who he had talked about. Chef was a generic name for commander, but that is how Paul referred to his friend. His unit is mentioned as 'Sturm Gesch. Lehr Brg 190'. This is also what **Deutsche Dienststelle** has on Paul for a unit. This was an Artillery unit that wore the uniforms of the Panzer troops. It also mentions he was in the Hospital or Lazarett' from January 3, 1944 to March 1, 1944. His last date in the German Army is probably June 14, 1945. The file also revealed he had been captured from May 8, 1945 until June 14, 1945.

From July 10, 1945, he worked as a Journeyman **Carpenter** as a civilian. The war was over for him. His **Denazification File** (from the Ludwigsburg Court in 1946) shows he was not considered a war criminal or high-level Nazi, but simply a follower.

Below is the **Order of Battle** for Sgt. Paul Ernst Kaess' unit:

Units:

Batterie Sturmartillerie-Abteilung 190

Sturmgeschütz-Abteilung 190 (Feb 41)

leichte Sturmgeschütz-Abteilung 190 (Apr 43)

leichte-Sturmgeschütz-Brigade 190 (Jan 44)

Order of Battle of above Units:

Oct 40 - formed at Jüterbog with three batteries Nov 40 - declared ready for combat Nov

40 - transferred to Lure, France Jan 41 - arrived in Balaci, Romania

Apr 41 - XXX Corps, 12th Army, the Balkans Apr/May 41 - participated in the invasion of Greece 15 May 41 ordered from Athens to Romania

Jun 41 - arrived in Bucharest, Romania

Jun 41 - 11th Army Reserves, Army Group South (less 1./ XI Corps, 11st Army) Jul/Aug 41 - assigned to IX Corps, 11st Army, Army Group South

Jul 41 - XI Corps, 11th Army, Army Group South (less 1./ assigned to XXX Corps)

Sep 41 - XXX Corps, 11th Army, Army Group South (later LIV Corps, 11th Army, Army Group South, less one battery assigned to XXX Corps)

Oct 41 - LIV Corps, 11th Army, Army Group South

Apr 42 - assigned to XXX Corps, 11st Army, Army Group South

Apr/May 42 - 6 long-barreled StuGs received and participated in the attack on Kertch
 42 - LIV Corps, 11th Army, Army Group South, conquest of Sevastopol (6 StuGs with L/43 guns)
 Jul 42 - refitting in the Yalta area; transferred to the Kursk area and assigned to 2nd Army
 Aug 42 - 14 long-barreled StuGs arrive
 Sep 42 - 12 more long-barreled StuGs arrive; 27 StuGs operational
 Jan 43 - refitting in Treuenbrietzen, reorganized with each batterie having a section of StuH 42s
 Mar 43 - 3./ attached to 168th Infantry Division, Corps Raus z.b.V., with one StuG Jun 43 - returned to the East, Army Group Center reserve (22 StuG III and 9 StuH 42 operational)
 Jul 43 - reached Karachev and assigned to 4th Army, Army Group Center Sep 43 - XXVII Corps, 4th Army, Army Group Center
 Nov 43 - transferred to the Vitebsk-Nevel area under 3rd Panzer Army Feb 44 - transferred to the Kovel area
 May 44 - transferred to the Mogilev area, 4th Army, Army Group Center Sep 44 - XX Corps, 2nd Army, Army Group Center
 Oct 44 - XXIII Corps, 2nd Army, Army Group Center Nov 44 - ordered to the rear for refitting
 Jan 45 - ordered back to the front near Danzig under the Second Army

(Summary)

Note Paul stepped off with his unit on the 1st day of **Operation Barbarossa**², the German invasion of the **Soviet Union** in June 1941. He was in the thick of it. Note also that Paul stated that he fought at the **Battle of Kursk** (1943)³ and likely fought at the **Battle of Sevastopol** (1942). At Kursk, he must have felt, during the battle, with machines constantly belching fire at each other, that 'Hell itself had usurped the place of earth.' It must have appeared as a blasted landscape that screamed of something unholy. These latter two battles are not mentioned in any depth here except to say Paul was likely awarded his **Iron Crosses at Kursk** and was likely wounded at Sevastopol. His unit was likely in the **Northern salient at Kursk**, on the periphery or fringes, and was pulled into the battle as the order went down for 'lotte, dotte, and everybody to help.' His unit likely acted as garrison troops in **France** in 1940. He had a **French** girlfriend (unknown name), and married a **Silesian** girl in Ratibor (now Raciborz, Poland) during wartime in 1944. Family stated he fought in **Yugoslavia** versus partisans. He was also stationed in **Bulgaria/Romania**. He probably stepped off with the German Army during **Operation Marita**⁴ on April 6, 1941, joining the Axis armoured thrust west (from **Bulgaria**) into **Yugoslavia**, and later south towards **Thessaloniki**.

² See *Operation Barbarossa: Hitler's Invasion of Russia 1941* (2011) by David Glantz & *Thesis: Operation Barbarossa* (2025) by Ajah Nashreine at Academia.edu.

³ See *The Battle of Kursk* (1999) by David Glantz & Jonathan M. House.

⁴ For information on Operation Marita and the Greek Campaign of 1941, see video *Kings and Generals: Battle of Greece and Battle of Crete: WWII Documentary*. Also see *Swastika Over the Acropolis: Re-interpreting the Nazi Invasion of Greece in World War II* (2013), by Craig A J Stockings & Eleanor Hancock.

He also made it to **Athens** during the Greek Campaign. Arnhild Kaess stated in a letter once that Paul 'had fought partisans in **Yugoslavia**' during the war. One wonders if she meant the **Greek Campaign** of 1941, or later (likely the former). Paul spent time in a Field Hospital in **Crimea** in 1942. He was in the German hospital in **Warsaw** in 1944. Arnhild Kaess stated that he may have served in **Poland**, and she probably meant his hospital stay there. He also spent time in hospital in **Hannover, Germany** in 1944, but that may have been related to his stay in **Warsaw**. It looks like he was pulled to the rear at that point. Paul stated he was wounded in **Vilnius, Lithuania**, in 1944 when a **Russian** soldier threw a grenade into his armoured vehicle. The date of injury that Brian remembers Paul giving him is November 11, 1944 or December 11, 1944. Paul showed Brian the 'soft skin' on the back of his skull where he had suffered his wound from 1944 that was still present in 1990. So, the question remains whether the above story (that Paul tells) relates to his 2nd and 3rd stay in hospital as mentioned in his **Deutsche Dienststelle** file, or represents an undocumented injury that occurred later in the war, when maintaining such paperwork became less robust. It wasn't unheard of for Hitler to send 'stomach-and-ears' battalions (i.e wounded soldiers) to the front. Arnhild Kaess stated that her father Paul had told her such terrible stories about the war that she was not able to repeat them. In 1990, Paul told Brian once that he saw someone's head (or 'kopf') fly off during battle. He said his friend **Chef** was killed late in the war. Paul was captured by the Allies on May 8, 1945 (**V-E Day**). He was released in June 14, 1945, going back to work as a Carpenter by mid-July 1945.

(Vilinius Campaign)

Dr. Gintautas Surgaitis sent an article regarding the **Battle of Vilnius** in the 'Karo archive 'See 'Battles for Vilnius: July 6–13, 1944' article in "Karo archyvas" or Military Archive Magazine by Dr. Vitalija Stravinskienė of the Lithuanian Institute of History. Written in Lithuanian. This article was recommended by Dr. Gintautas Surgaitis, editor of above journal. gintautas.surgailis@lka.lt

On April 3, 2025, Karile Vaitkute, email: karile@balzekasmuseum.org, a Genealogist with the Balzekas Museum, suggested I contact Dr. Gintautas Surgaitis of Lithuania, a military historian & editor-in-chief of the "Karo archyvas" (Military Archive) magazine, at gintautas.surgailis@lka.lt

Here is some summary information below translated from the **Vilnius** article:

The **Battle for Vilnius** was fought from July 6-13, 1944. The Battle was fought between the German Army (about 3000 soldiers in **Festung Vilnius** or Fortress Vilnius, aka '**the Vilnius Cauldron**'), the Polish Home Army (AK or **Armia Krakowia**), and the **Soviet Red Army**. Each group had different goals. The Poles had initiated a '**Gate of Dawn**' operation. On the night of July 6, 1944 the Poles had initiated the battle to force the Germans to withdraw. The Vilnius and Novgorod regions of the **Home Army** attacked from four directions, but the main blow was to come from the southeast. This was done by a total of 12,000 **Polish Home Army** soldiers. The Poles expected the **Red Army** to appear on July 12, but they arrived much earlier. German Engineers had arrived in April (on Hitler's Order) to turn Vilnius into an impregnable fortress. Vilnius had strategic

importance as a railway junction and opened the way to East Prussia.

There were **three** phases to the battle:

- 1) the *initial Polish* attacks,
- 2) the *arrival and encirclement* of the city by the **Red Army** (under the **3rd Belorussian Front**) on July 8-9.
- 3) The decisive battles of July 10-13. **Polish partisans**, along with **Soviet soldiers** continued *storming* Vilnius.

On July 6-7, 1944, about 4,500 soldiers of the **Polish Home Army** began to storm German positions. The light weapons of the Poles were no match for the German heavy machine guns. Fierce fighting broke out in the center. Entire blocks were bombed and burned out. The **Red Army** was concentrated in the eastern part of the city. Some of the retreating German soldiers died in the battle near the village of **Kriaučiūnai**, when they encountered partisans of the **Home Army**. **Gen. Reiner Stahel** managed to join up with the forces of **Gen. T. Tolsdorf** and retreat in the direction of **Kaunas**. About 2,000 Germans managed to make a 'breakout' from the city. Several hundred of them died or were captured while crossing the **Neris**. By July 13, there were no Germans left in the City. About 2,500 German soldiers died in the battle in July. Soviet sources indicate 8,000 Germans killed in the **Vilnius Cauldron**, but these figures may be exaggerated. Over 3 thousand soldiers are buried in the **Antakalnis military cemetery**. Perhaps Chef is buried here. It seems that number of casualties on both sides should grow.

During archaeological research during the **Soviet** period and after the restoration of Lithuanian independence, more buried **German** soldiers and **Red Army** soldiers were found in various parts of Vilnius. After the battle, the streets were still littered with soldiers' bodies, fallen horses, broken guns and other military equipment. The entire Old Town and many other districts formed a single fire site. Some houses were destroyed by shells, others burned down. Smoke-filled chimneys stood around.

Another Vilnius resident's impressions: "Vilnius leaves a sad impression. Most of it is in ruins. Some quarters or streets are completely destroyed, such as German or New World." (now Naujininkai). Vilnius lost over 40% of its buildings during the war.

(Testimony)

Paul had mentioned '**Chivalry**' once to Brian regarding his exploits during WWII, but Brian was aware that the **German Army** had orders not to even take female Russian soldiers as prisoners, so this was certainly left in doubt. Perhaps Paul meant that he was usually involved in fighting regular combat formations and was not involved in SS or Einsatzgruppen activities or pogroms or large scale atrocities such as **Babi Yar**. Nonetheless, the **German Army** was certainly 'in the know' on many of these activities, and Paul's complicity in this regard cannot be denied⁵. Indeed, with 20 million Russian soldiers and civilians killed during the war, not all could be blamed on Stalin, as the Red Army told the Allies at the end of the conflict. Paul mentioned that he had applied for

⁵ See *They Thought They Were Free: The Germans 1933-45* (1955) by Milton Mayer. I read this work in my undergrad days at Northeastern Illinois University as a History minor.

and been rejected from the SS (or Schutzstaffel) sometime during the war. Perhaps he applied at the outset, when enthusiasm must have been at its highest. Moreover, perhaps Paul saw himself and his comrade's actions in the light of previous **Germanic Crusades** in the East when the **Teutonic Knights** had received the full support of a **Papal Bull** to quell the Infidel or **Pagan Slavs**. Perhaps they 'bought' **Goebbels** propaganda or his narrative of Eastern Bolshevism as a threat to 'Western civilization' (noted in his Sportpalast speech of February 1943), where **Goebbels** wanted to save 'Western civilization' from Bolshevik Decay. The ordinary 'soldaten' probably just wanted to survive. Human rights and international law were still in a fledgling stage, so to speak, and the Germans may have had no problem with imposing 'the right of the stronger' on their foes. **Paul** also wrote that he ran for a local office in Benningen am Neckar, sometime in 1944-45. Perhaps he was riding his 'coat tails' as a War Hero, being decorated in 1943. It was obvious that Doris didn't seem to mind, with her father Viktor Dorschke being an ardent Nazi. This may have paved the way for their nuptials in 1944.

(Other Players)

Sgt. Paul Ernst Kaess wasn't the only person in his family or entourage to serve the Germans during WWII. There were certainly others, many preciously close to him. His brother **Lt. Emil Karl Kaess** was reputed to be a German Army Cavalry Officer, who was captured during the **Battle of Stalingrad**⁶, and managed to 'barter' himself back to freedom in 1946, by claiming to be a rich man. Paul's brother-in-law **Jaeger Arnold Dorschke** was killed in the German Army in 1945, just five days before Hitler's death. Paul's other brother-in-law **LCpl. Willy Assenheimer** was killed in the German Army in France in late 1944. **Elsa Frieda (Kulhanek) Barmus** kept a picture/painting of her father Willy in his German Army uniform in the basement of her home in Oak Lawn, Illinois for many years. **Rudi Dorschke**, another brother-in-law, served in the German Navy during the war, surviving the conflict. **Cpl. Eduard Viktor Dorschke**, another brother-in-law, served as a Luftwaffe Flak Gunner and was happy to show Brian his Mercedes-Benz in 1990 and urged Brian to place flowers on **Doris'** grave.

(The Provenance of the Kaess Family Heirloom)

In 1990, **Paul Ernst Kaess** gifted to his paternal grandson **Brian Paul Kaess** a **Kaess Family Heirloom** (containing roughly 50-100 vintage black-and-white iconic family photos from the WWII era), papers detailing a Kaess family genealogy spanning to the middle ages, and more. In the Kaess family home in Benningen, Brian even remembers opening (on the 1st floor) a dresser drawer filled with family photos, many controversially of Paul while he was in the Hitler Youth in the 1930's. The Kaess Family Heirloom subsequently made its way to Chicago, where it stayed in the apartment of **Garret Thomas Kaess** from 1990-93 on the SW side, then was held by **Brian Paul Kaess** in his studio apartment in the Kadin Building (also Chicago) from 1993 to 1996. Consequently, from 1996 to about 2001 or so, the Heirloom was held in trust with **Garret Thomas Kaess** in New Lenox, Illinois. From about 2001 to 2020 or so, it was held in trust by **Garret Thomas Kaess** in his family home in Noblesville, Indiana. From 2020 to the present (2025), it has been held by Garret Thomas Kaess, once more in trust, at his apartment in Indianapolis, Indiana.

⁶ See *Enemy at the Gates: The Battle for Stalingrad* (1973) by William Craig.

I would hope, that in the future, my son **Paul Jesus Kaess Urbina**, would have a say as to the final disposition of the Kaess Family Heirloom. I would be willing to sign a specific bequest or legacy to this effect.

Images:

Upper Left: Sgt. Paul Ernst Kaess & Dorothea 'Doris' Dorschke on their wedding day on March 14, 1944, at St. Johannes Täuf. Ostrog Catholic Church in Ratibor, Upper Silesia, Germany (now Poland). Credit: Kaess Family Heirloom.

Upper Right: Sgt. Paul Ernst Kaess. He served in the German Army during WWII from 1940 to 1945, surrendering on May 8, 1945 (V-E Day). Credit: Kaess Family Heirloom.

Bottom Left: Sgt. Paul Ernst Kaess during wartime in Europe. Credit: Kaess Family Heirloom.

Bottom Right: 'Chef', Paul's friend in the German Army, who was killed late in the war. 'Chef' may be a generic name for commander. Here he is shown wonderfully posing with a pipe. Credit: Kaess Family Heirloom.

Image 1 (Upper Left): Paul Ernst Kaess wearing the uniform of the RAD or Reich Labor Force, just prior to his enlistment in the German Army in WWII. Credit: Kaess Family Heirloom.

Image 2 (Upper Right): Sgt. Paul Ernst Kaess with his comrades during wartime in WWII. He is reaching into his leather jacket for something unknown. Credit: Kaess Family Heirloom.

Image 3 (Bottom Left): Sgt. Paul Ernst Kaess, standing on the far left, with his comrades in the German Army during WWII. Paul looks young here and Brian speculates that this may have been during the Greek Campaign. Credit: Kaess Family Heirloom.

Image 4 (Bottom Right): An image of a German armoured vehicle emerging from a forest during WWII, with commander on top (possibly Paul?). This vehicle was likely either a Stug III or Mark III or Mark IV tank, likely the former because of its size. Credit: Kaess Family Heirloom.

Image 5 (Top Left): Sgt. Paul Ernst Kaess (in middle) with Dorothea Dorschke on his left, amidst the company of other comrades and friends. Taken during wartime. They appear dressed for chilly weather. Credit: Kaess Family Heirloom.

Image 6 (Top Right): Taken in 1951, this image shows the Kaess Family of Doris (Dorschke) Kaess, her son Gerd Edwin Paul Kaess, and husband Paul Ernst Kaess. She was suffering illness at this time, possibly Leukemia, and died in December of that year. Credit: Kaess Family Heirloom.

Image 7 (Bottom Left): Paul Ernst Kaess (in the 1960's) at a family party or gathering, with his daughter Arnhild Kaess (on his left) by his side. Paul was working as a 'carpenter' or 'cabinet maker' or sitzmobil tischler' at this time, just like his father and grandfather before him. Credit: Ester Kaess.

Image 8 (Bottom Right): Paul Ernst Kaess (in center) standing with his daughter Arnhild Kaess (on left) and niece Elsa Frieda (Kulhanek) Barmus (on right) in Germany in 1989. This was during Elsa's trip to Germany in 1989. She was the 1st person from the Kulhanek Family to make contact with Garret Kaess in Chicago in 1990. Garret's Polish landlord Stanislaus told him: 'Garret! Your German cousin is here!' Credit: Arnhild Kaess.

Image 9 (Upper Left): Kaess Family Photo at the 1988 baptism of Nadja Vogel in SW Germany. From L-R: Paul Ernst Kaess, his 2nd wife Hildegard Louise Golz, Priest/Pastor, Achim's sister, Achim Vogel, Ursula (Kaess) Vogel, Arnhild Kaess, Achim's brother holding baby Nadja, & Achim's parents. Credit: Ursula Kaess.

Image 10 (Upper Right): Paul Ernst Kaess & his grandson Brian Paul Kaess hugging outside his home on In Den Hofackern 5 in the small village of Benningen am Neckar, Germany, during Brian's trip to Europe in 1990. Brian & Paul & Arnhild Kaess had exchanged letters from 1989 on. Credit: Brian Paul Kaess.

Image 11 (Bottom Left): Paul Ernst Kaess & his friend Martin Heim standing in Paul's vineyard, circa 1990, on the right bank of the Neckar River, Germany. Paul's favorite wines were Trollinger and Lemberger, both local varieties, and he would grow these himself. Brian would have hoped he would have left the vineyard to his grandson, like 'a vineyard left to criminals' as in the Bible. But like Victor Fargas says in the Ninth Gate (1999), 'Old families wither and die.' Credit: Martin Heim.

Image 12 (Bottom Right): Paul Ernst Kaess in the nursing home of the Hospitalers or 'Johanniterorden,' in Pleidelsheim, Germany, in 1996. Brian Paul Kaess came to see his grandpa for the last time with his friend Sven Urbatschek, at Sven's urging. Brian was grateful to hug his grandpa and was happy that, even in illness, Paul still had a grin on his face. Credit: Brian Paul Kaess.

For the Battle of Vilnius, see the article (in Lithuanian) on page 162 of following link:
https://kam.lt/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/KARO-ARCHYVAS-XXXVIII_e15.pdf

Relevant **blogs/posts** about **Sgt. Paul Ernst Kaess**, all created by **Brian Paul Kaess**, include ones at **find a grave**, **axis history forum**, **forum der wehrmacht**, **feldgrau**, **WW II Forums**, **Ahnenforschung.net Forum**, & **History Hub**. **History Hub** has the largest cache of documents on Paul, along with **FS Gallery**, & the '**Brian Paul Kaess Genealogy**' community folder at Zenodo.org (CERN). These are shown below:

https://es.findagrave.com/memorial/201044976/paul_ernst-kaess

<https://forum.axishistory.com/viewtopic.php?t=245640>

<https://www.forum-der-wehrmacht.de/index.php?thread/49599-sgt-paul-ernst-kaess-in-batterie-sturm-artillerie-abteilung-190/>

<https://feldgrau.net/forum/viewtopic.php?t=35398>

<https://ww2f.com/threads/sgt-paul-ernst-kaess-1921-2002-german-army-in-wwii.55310/>

<https://forum.ahnenforschung.net/forum/allgemeine-diskussionsforen/militaerbezogene-familiengeschichtsforschung/150362-sgt-paul-ernst-kaess-1921-2002>

<https://historyhub.history.gov/military-records/f/military-records-forum/22146/seeking-name-of-german-veterans-affairs-agency>

<https://historyhub.history.gov/military-records/f/military-records-forum/15476/looking-for-pow-records-for-german-world-war-ii-soldier>